

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN ONLINE SHOPPING IN AMAZON

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Abstract:

Online shopping means electronic commerce. Consumers buy products over the internet using a web browser or mobile applications. In the modern technology, most companies rely on electronic shopping for attracting new and existing customers. Amazon is the most popular and trustworthy website in online shopping. Amazon has offered a wide range of products to customers. Customer satisfaction is based on the price, quality, offers, discounts, fast delivery, secured payment, and return policy of the product. The aim of the study is to analyze the factors that influence customer satisfaction with Amazon online shopping. This research was collected from 250 respondents by using a Google forms. In this study tools used Percentage analysis, Friedman ranking test, ANOVA Test. The study concludes majority of the respondents are satisfying on Amazon online shopping.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Amazon, Customer Satisfaction, Product, Experience

Introduction:

E-commerce has grown rapidly with the development of the internet and due to the easy availability of internet. Online shopping is using everywhere in the world. The advantages of online shopping are working 24/7/365 and fast delivery. Customers have placed a direct order for something they need through online. Online shopping is very easy to use without leaving their residence. The customers are buying brands from seller over through internet. Online shopping makes it easier for the customer to choose the variety of products or brands. Consumers are always on the lookout for new products as well as appealing offers or discounts. Online shopping has helps to customers save their time and money. In India, Amazon is the most famous website used by customers for the purchase of products Amazon mission is "To be Earth's most customer – centric company where people can find and discover anything they want to buy online". Based on the mission, Amazon focused their strategies for customer convenience and service. Amazon has to reach largest customers to satisfy the existing and new customers. Customer's positive experience has to develop their loyalty. The purpose of this paper is to analyze customer preference and satisfaction for Amazon online purchases.

Review of Literature:

Prof. Dr. Vrushali M. Shitole et al., (2022) focused on the consumer purchasing habits and how satisfied consumers with Amazon services. The main objects of the study impact on consumer satisfaction on online shopping. The sample size was 201 and analyzed used tools were simple percentage analysis, ANOVA, chi-square and cross tab. In this study founded majority (65.8%) of respondents have been buying online shopping for more than two years. The authors concluded that Amazon concentrated on innovation of new brands, expanded their communities and improve the quality of products. These recommendations are help to attract new customers.

Dr. Saravanan. S et al., (2021) examined to avoid some uncertainty fact the customers face in the shopping through online. The study focused to marketing strategies and consumer attributes of online shopping. In this study collected 100 respondents and used more tools in the study and analysed with the help of mathematical and statistical tools. The study concluded that the consumers looked for good quality of products, timely service, security and privacy in payment method.

Dr. Tamilarasi. S et al., (2019) focused on consumers play a several roles for the decision of purchasing a greater number of purchases. The main objectives of the study were consumer perception of Amazon on seasonal offers and analyse the satisfaction level with relating gender. A sample size was 200 and convenience sampling was used. The tools of the study were percentage and Mann Whitney U test. The study founded online shoppers in Amazon are high in female category in gender and in the age of 20-28 years. Concluded of the study that Amazon satisfied the consumer and providing good services and getting satisfied in the seasonal offers.

Kavitha T. (2017) examined the level of consumer satisfaction towards Amazon online shopping. In this study used a sample size of 100 respondents on the basis of random sampling method. The study suggested

that online shopping should improve their promotional and service strategies and build up positive perception on consumer online shopping.

Objectives:

- To identify factors influencing of customers satisfaction in online shopping.
- To find out demographic factors and customer using behaviour among the respondents.
- To determine the rank towards reasons and product category influence to buy on Amazon online shopping.
- To analyse difference between demographic factors and customer satisfaction on Amazon online shopping.

Research Methodology:

The study is descriptive in nature. Convenience sampling method was adopted for this study. The data were collected by Google forms from 250 respondents for who are using Amazon online shopping. Data were collected through primary data and secondary data. The tools were used percentage analysis, Friedman ranking test and one - way ANOVA test.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Factors	Category	Percent
Age	20 - 30	62.7
Gender	Female	60.2
Educational Qualification	College (UG / PG)	51.8
Occupation	Salaried	47.4
Monthly Income	Below 25000	48.6
Marital Status	Unmarried	55.4

Sources: Primary Data

- 62.7% of the respondents of the study belongs to the age group of 20 - 30, 20.1% belongs to the age group of 31 - 40, 10.8% belongs to the age group of 41 - 50 and 6.4% belongs to the age group of above 50.
- According to the gender: female - 60.2% of the respondents and male - 39.8% of the respondents.
- According to the educational qualification: 51.8% of the respondents were college (UG /PG), 21.7% of the respondents were professionals, 16.1% of the respondents were diploma and 10.4% of the respondents were other qualification.
- According to the occupation: 47.4% of the respondents belong to the salaried people, 28.9% of the respondents belong to the self-employed, and 16.1% of the respondents belong to the own business and 7.6% of the respondents belongs to the house wife.
- 48.6% of the respondents falls under the income group of Rs. Below 25000, 33.7% of the respondents falls under the income group 25001 - 50000, 12% of the respondents falls under the income group 50001 - 70000 and 5.6% of the respondents falls under the income group of above 75000.
- According to the marital status: 55.4% of the respondents were unmarried and 44.6% of the respondents were married.

Table 2: Customer Using Behavior

Variable	Classification	Percent
Duration	1 - 3 years	41.4
Time spending for shopping	Once a month	36.9
Mode of payments	Cash on delivery	39.4
Amount spend for shopping	Rs. 1000 - Rs. 3000	39.4
Rate the quality of products	Good	59.8
Defects on online shopping	Cheap quality of products	30.1
Rate the delivery experience	Good	55.8
Uniqueness in service of Amazon	Quality product	37.3

Sources: Primary Data

- Duration: 41.4% majority of the respondents were used 1 - 3 years, 27.7% of the respondents were used less than 1 year, 19.7% of the respondents were used 4 - 5 years and 11.2% of the respondents were used more than 5 years.
- The time spending for shopping: 36.9% majority of the respondents were shopped once a month, 25.7% of the respondents was shopped every 2 or 3 months, 16.5% of the respondents were shopped weekly once, 11.2% of the respondents were shopped every day and 9.6% of the respondents were shopped twice a month.
- Mode of payments: 39.4% is majority of the respondents were used cash on delivery category,

- 23.3% of the respondents were used net banking, 20.1% of the respondents were used credit card and 17.3% of the respondents were used debit card.
- Amount spend for shopping: 39.4% of the respondents were spend the amount of Rs. 1000 - Rs. 3000, 32.1% of the respondents were spend the amount of Rs. 500 - Rs.1000, 12.9% of the respondents were spend the amount of Rs. below 500, 11.2% of the respondents were spend the amount Rs. 3000 - Rs. 5000 and 4.4% of the respondents were spend the amount of Rs. above 5000.
- Rate the quality of products: 59.8% majority of the respondents were given good in quality, 18.9% of the respondents were given fair in quality, 18.1% of the respondents were given very good in quality and 3.2% of the respondents were given poor in quality.
- Defects on online shopping: 30.1% of the respondents were said cheap quality of products, 26.5% of the respondents were said damage products, 25.7% of the respondents were said delay in delivery, 10.4% of the respondents were said non - delivery products and 7.2% of the respondents were said wrong delivery.
- Rate the delivery experience: majority 55.8% of the respondents were replied good in delivery experience, 19.7% of the respondents were replied fair in delivery experience, 17.7% of the respondents were replied very good in delivery experience and 6.8% of the respondents were replied poor in delivery experience.
- Uniqueness in service of Amazon satisfied as compared to other shopping applications: 37.3% of the respondents were said product quality, 28.1% of the respondents were said fast delivery, 27.7% of the respondents were said reasonable return or exchange policy and 6.8% of the respondents were said transaction security.

Table 3: Friedman Test on reason influenced to buy

H0: there is no significant association between mean rank towards reasons influence to buy on Amazon online shopping.

Reasons	Mean Rank
Less Price	2.84
Good Quality	2.95
Fast Delivery	3.03
Standard	3.15
More Options	3.03
N	249
Chi-Square	7.192
DF	4
Asymp. Sig.	.126

Sources: Primary Data

The above table 3 shows that Chi-Square value is 7.192, P value is more than 0.05 the null hypothesis is at accepted at 5% level of significant. Hence conclude that there is no significant association between mean rank towards reasons influence to buy on Amazon online shopping. Based on mean value, 3.15 is the first rank most of the respondents preferred to “standard of products”, second rank (3.03) preferred to “fast delivery and more options”, third rank (2.95) preferred “good quality” and fourth rank (2.84) preferred to “less price of products”.

Table 4: Friedman Test on product category

H0: there is no significant association between mean rank towards product category influence to buy on Amazon online shopping

Product Category	Mean Rank
Clothing	3.71
Books & Media	3.84
Fashion& Jewels	4.07
Electronics	4.21
Stationery	4.11
Toys & Games	4.30
Home décor items	3.74
N	249
Chi-Square	24.690
DF	6
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Sources: Primary Data

The above table 4 indicates that Chi-Square value is 24.690, P value is less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is at rejected at 1% level of significance. Hence conclude that there is significant association between mean rank towards product category influence to buy on Amazon online shopping. Based on the mean value, 4.30 is the first rank most of the respondents preferred to “toys& games”, second rank (4.21) preferred “electronics”, third rank (4.11) preferred “stationery”, fourth rank (4.07) preferred “fashion &jewels”, fifth rank (3.84) preferred “books & media”, sixth rank (3.74) preferred “home décor items” and seventh rank (3.71) preferred “clothing”.

Suggestions:

- Online retailers must upgrade their well-equipped shipping in order to deliver their goods. Most buyers are not happy with the way that the goods are packaged.
- The misuse of credit cards must be prevented on the part of the merchant.
- Retailers must make sure that the consumer receives the refund for the returned item as quickly as possible.
- Customers do not generally have positive opinions of most internet retailers. To boost their reputation in the industry, internet company companies should provide the customers with what they want.
- Internet retailers should behave honestly and sincerely in their commercial relationships.
- The online store’s search options ought to correspond to the items its client’s are looking for. The majority of the website shouldn’t match the product they were looking for.
- There are fewer people who shop online since there is a lack of post-purchase support. As a result, the service providers handle it.
- Products that need after-sale service should offer this service to draw in additional customers.
- Customers should receive proper instruction on how to do online transactions and the measures they should take.
- The business needs to increase client payment security.
- After a purchase, Amazon could start asking for comments from customers and paying extra attention to those who are dissatisfied by setting up a call back from their customer service team.

Conclusion:

The technology has opened new doors and opportunities that enable for a more convenient lifestyle of people. Online shopping is growing business in India. It provides purchasing more opportunity to the customers. This paper focused customer satisfaction towards Amazon online shopping. The result of the study that majority of the respondents are satisfying with the standard, quality, brand, best price, variety, offers, fast delivery and return policy of the products by Amazon online shopping.

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